

AUTOMATED IDENTIFICATION OF FISH SPECIES USING YOLOv7

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Abstract— Deep learning is subset of machine learning, which is essentially a neural network with three or more layers which attempt to simulate the behavior of human brain. This research is about an automated system for identification and classification of fish species. It helps the marine biologists and fisherman to have greater understanding of the fish species and their habitats. The goal of study is to create a "Automated identification of Fish species using YOLOv7" model. The most recent study in this area classified different types of fish using deep learning. Convolutional Layer or Convolutional Neural Networks make up a majority of the deep learning models utilized (CNN). This research experimented with using object detection method based on YOLOv7, which possible to recognize the species of fish inside of the image without more image preprocessing. This research aimed to know the performance of the YOLOv7 method against other object detection methods like CNN, RCNN in fish species detection. CNN struggle to categories photos with various positions. A single-stage real-time object detector is YOLOv7. YOLOv7 introduces a number of architectural improvements that increase efficiency and accuracy. The accuracy of the YOLOv7 reached 91.4 % far above the accuracy of the Convolution Neural Network Model with an accuracy of 61.4 %

Keywords—*You Only Look Once version 7, AI Artificial Intelligence, CNN Convolution Neural Network, RCNN Region-based Convolution Neural Network, Deep Learning*

Introduction

This research is about an automated system for identification and classification of fish species. It helps the marine biologists and fisherman to have greater understanding of the fish species and their habitats. The goal of study is to create a "Automated identification of Fish species using YOLOv7" model. With high-quality protein and a wide range of vitamins and minerals, fish is a significant source of essential nutrients. It is used by people as food all around the world. Fish with jaws and fish without jaws belong into two different types. The deep learning method based on convolution neural networks is applied in a number of fields. A number of research are presently using the revised model known as YOLOv7. In terms of visual recognition, a convolution neural network-based algorithm can be implemented quickly. An method named as YOLOv7 that is based on deep learning is used to identify species in pictures (You Only Look Once version 7). The real-time object detection accuracy is significantly increased by YOLOv7 without raising inference costs. In general, YOLOv7 offers a

quicker and more stable network architecture that offers a better feature integration method, more accurate object recognition performance, a more robust algorithm, and an improved 1 label assignment and training and testing efficiency. The shape of fish's heads, the location of their mouths, the type and location of their fins, and their average adult size are some attributes that set them apart. When combined with other characteristics like geographic range, colour patterns like vertical stripes or fin patterns may also aid in identifying fish. However, utilizing fish photos and videos taken underwater, automated methods for fish species recognition can enhance the outcomes and enable in more comprehensive scientific investigations of fish behaviour. Pattern matching, physical and statistical behaviour, and feature extraction are the basic elements for automated fish recognition. For fish species counting, population estimates, fish counting, the research of fish associations, and ecosystem management, fish recognition is also crucial. Machine learning is used to classify the species of underwater fish for massive datasets. YOLOv7 have a good accuracy rate.

I. OBJECTIVE OF THE PROJECT

Traditionally, external physical characteristics have been used to identify fish species. An experienced fishery specialist and well-trained fishermen follow this identifying method. For the average person, it is a very difficult task to identify every type of fish. Most recently, a technique for automatic species identification in images was created. In this technique, the software uses a user-provided fish photo as input to identify the fish to a taxonomic level. If the species of fish that is captured does not match the database of the input species, then the image of the fish is captured, and later the user is prompted to give the data for the species if known. The automated fish recognition 2 is mainly based on pattern matching, physical and statistical behavior and features extraction. Neural Network: Neural network is a sequence of algorithms that try to build the relationships between the data and the human brain. Neural networks adapt the changing input so, the network generates the best possible output without needs to redesign again. Yolo v7: The object identification algorithm YOLOv7 was developed using PyTorch as its development framework. It is renowned for its ability to recognise items in a live setting. It is an excellent method that provides answers to numerous difficulties in

practical computer vision. YOLOv7 proposes the usage of an end-to-end neural network that provides predictions of bounding boxes and class probabilities all at once, in contrast to the strategy used by object detection algorithms before it, which repurposed classifiers to do detection.

II. SCOPE OF THE PROJECT

Fish identification algorithms are created for Marine biologist and fisherman to identifying the fish species. The Fish recognition algorithm will be replaced by a web application and cameras. The most recent method just detects the object without classifying its categories or specifications. With this approach, objects will be identified along with their kinds and specifications. The instance segmentation in Yolo v7 algorithm identify the species once it is viewed and fast segmentation helps in identifying the species model both in image and video format. YOLO has the natural advantage of speed in addition to better Intersection over Union in bounding boxes and improved prediction accuracy when compared to real-time object detectors. When compared to its competitors, YOLO runs at speeds of up to 36 FPS and box AP 56.8. Many of the existing model's performance can be improved through techniques known as "bag of freebies" without incurring an increase in training expenses. These BoF techniques have been introduced by YOLOv7. In the range of 5 FPS to 160 FPS, all YOLOv7 devices outperform earlier object detectors in terms of speed and accuracy. When compared to the competition, the YOLOv7 model is more efficient in terms of Average Precision (AP) and speed.

LITERATURE SURVEY

Convolutional neural networks are utilised for object detection and classification in this research by B. S. Rekha, Sravan Kumar Reddy, et al. The system consists of augmentation, detection, and classification stages. An augmentation procedure was conducted to overcome the overfitting problem. A more diversified dataset to develop standardized pre-processing and augmentation that improves trained models and binary classifier is used. VGG-16 classifier used in the classification of the fishes. Aditya Agarwal et al in 2020, This model is designed to detect fish, a specific type of object. Multiple layers and stages for detection, such as augmentation, segmentation, masking, and other approaches, were included in the model. They used the F-RCNN framework, which is an improved version of the R-CNN framework, for implementation. X. Yang et al in 2020, In this study, the Resnet101 network model served as the feature extractor, and the feature pyramid network and Resnet101 were combined to create the backbone network. R. Mandal and co. The Region of Interest (RoI) in this study is classified and localised using the mask R-CNN algorithm. By anticipating a segmentation mask on the Region of Interest (RoI), it improves upon existing frameworks and provides the best performance output for deep learning models. In this paper, K. He, G. Gkioxari, and others present two-stage RPN (Region Proposal Network) and Fast RCNN techniques for Mask R-CNN. Fast R-CNN is used by RoI (Regions of Interest) to extract the object's features, apply a bounding box to the object, and recover mask structures from fully connected layers. Deep networks have been used in several studies to predict object bounding boxes. S Ren and others In terms of detection accuracy, Region Proposal Networks with

Fast R-CNNs perform better than the strong baseline of selective search with Fast R-CNNs.

III. METHODOLOGY

YOLO A single-stage real-time object detector is YOLO. It is currently the quickest and most precise real-time object detector. By improving upon its previous performance, YOLOv7 created a notable benchmark. FCNN (Fully Connected Neural Network) underpins the YOLO design. However, the YOLO family has lately expanded to include variations based on Transformers. Transformer-based detectors will be covered in a future post. There are three primary parts to the YOLO framework are Backbone, Head and Neck. The Backbone primarily collects the most important facts from an image and sends them to the Head through the Neck. The Head makes data pyramids by compiling feature maps that the Backbone has retrieved. The head is finally made of the output layers and final detections. 10 Intersection over Union (IoU): Intersection over union is a key measure for evaluating the accuracy of object identification models' localization and detecting localization problems. For the purpose of calculating the IoU with the expectations and the ground truth, the union of the bounding boxes for a single estimate and the dataset bounding boxes for the same area acts as the starting point. The area that the two bounding boxes combined, usually referred to as the Union, is then calculated. The measure that the bounding box matches the original forecast may be calculated by multiplying the intersection by the union, which provides us the ratio of the overlap to the total area. Intersection over Union Average Precision (AP): The average precision is calculated as the area under a precision against recall curve for a collection of predictions. Recall is established by dividing all of the model's predictions for a class by all of the labels that have already been provided to that class. On the other hand, accuracy is defined as the proportion of true positives to all of the predictions the model made. By analyzing the area under the precision against recall curve, people can figure out the average precision for each class in the model. The term used to describe the average of this statistic across all classes is mean average precision (mAP).

YOLO V7: The YOLO algorithm divides the image into N grids, with an equal-sized $S \times S$ region in each grid. Each of these N grids is responsible for finding and locating the object it includes. The object label, likely that the object will be in the cell, and the B bounding box coordinates in relation to the object's cell coordinates are therefore predicted by these grids. This method greatly reduces processing because cells from the image handle both detection and recognition, but— It generates a lot of duplicate predictions since many cells predict the same object with various bounding box predictions. YOLO uses Non Maximal Suppression to deal with this problem. YOLOv7 has a number of structural advancements that enhance performance and precision. Similar to Scaled YOLOv4, YOLOv7 backbones do not use ImageNet pre-trained backbones. Instead, the models are trained using the entire COCO dataset. The similarity is predicted because Scaled YOLOv4, an extension of YOLOv4, was created by the same authors as YOLOv7. The key changes to the YOLOv7 are noted below.

- Architectural Reforms E-ELAN (Extended Efficient Layer Aggregation Network) Model Scaling for Concatenation12 based Models
- Trainable BoF (Bag of Freebies) Planned re-parameterized convolution and Coarse for auxiliary and Fine for lead loss

E-ELAN (Extended Efficient Layer Aggregation Network) The computational building piece of the YOLOv7 backbone is the E-ELAN. It draws influence from earlier studies on network effectiveness. It was created by looking at the following elements that affect speed and accuracy. Memory access cost I/O channel ratio Element wise operation Activations Gradient path Expand, shuffle, and merge cardinality are used in the suggested E-ELAN to continuously increase the network's learning ability while maintaining the original gradient path. The E-ELAN design, to put it simply, improves learning for the framework. It is built on the ELAN computing block.

IV. CONCLUSION

The paper addresses two important issues of a Fish Species detection — how to analyse the fish species for the fisherman, and how to identify the new species and extinction species from the Researcher side . The fish species is identified instantly using the instance segmentation by yolo v7 algorithm once the fish image is classified according to its species. The image is captured and it is a new species the image will be saved in the system for researcher. This project will give an higher performance in Fish species detection compared to others because it uses Yolo v7 E6e which moves 40 FPS and the precision is 56.8 compared other image detection algorithm yolo V7 has higher AP.

V. LIMITATIONS

Although YOLOv7 appears to be the greatest technique to apply when trying to solve an object detection problem, it has a number of drawbacks. Since each grid can only detect a single object, YOLOv7 struggles to identify and separate

small objects in photos where they occur in bunches. As a result, YOLOv7 has trouble locating and detecting little items that ordinarily form groups, like a line of ants. In comparison to significantly slower object identification techniques like Fast RCNN, YOLO also has lesser accuracy.

VI. FUTURE WORK

The future work of this paper is to develop a web application for fisherman and marine biologists, as well as implement the algorithm in the camera so that it automatically detects species. The automated fish recognition is primarily based on pattern matching, physical and statistical behavior, and features extraction specification and its attributes, which help fisherman identify rare species and determine whether the species is fishable or not.

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